

Encapsulated single garlic (*Allium sativum* L.) extract (E-SGE): A novel approach to inhibit adipogenesis in 3T3-L1 cells

Sri Rahayu Lestari¹, Putri Elok Septiana Dewi¹,
Dimas Nur Ramadhani³, Nenes Prastita³, Dewi Sekar Miasih¹, Yuslinda Annisa⁴,
Alif Rosyidah El Baroroh¹

1 Department of Biology, Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Science, Universitas Negeri Malang, Jl. Semarang No.5, Malang 65145, East Java, Indonesia Indonesia, Malang, Indonesia

2 Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Science, Universitas Negeri Malang, Jl. Semarang No.5, Malang 65145, East Java, Indonesia, Malang, Indonesia

3 Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Negeri Malang, Jl. Semarang No.5, Malang 65145, East Java, Indonesia Indonesia, Malang, Indonesia

4 Department of Biology, Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences, Universitas Brawijaya, Malang 65145, East Java Indonesia, Malang, Indonesia

Corresponding author: Sri Rahayu Lestari (sriahayulestari@um.ac.id)

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Abstract

Garlic (*Allium sativum* L.), a medicinal plant rich in bioactive compounds like allicin, ajoene, and alliin, is traditionally used to treat obesity and related disorders. However, its bioavailability is limited due to instability and poor solubility. To overcome these challenges, we encapsulated single garlic extract (SGE) in a chitosan-alginate matrix for enhancing stability and bioavailability. The morphological characteristics of the encapsulated particles were assessed via scanning electron microscopy (SEM), revealing them to be spherical, smooth, and porous. The cytotoxicity of encapsulated single garlic extract (E-SGE) was evaluated in 3T3-L1 cells using the MTT assay, and lipid accumulation during adipogenesis was monitored via Oil Red O (ORO) staining. Our results demonstrated that E-SGE significantly reduced lipid accumulation and inhibited adipogenesis in 3T3-L1 cells, as indicated by the decreased expression of adipogenic markers such as PPAR γ , C/EBP α , GLUT4, and adiponectin. These findings suggest that E-SGE holds promise as a functional anti-obesity agent by targeting adipogenesis and enhancing the bioavailability of bioactive garlic compounds.

Keywords

encapsulation, single garlic, adipogenesis

Introduction

Excess body weight beyond the usual range (overweight) is a prevalent occurrence in contemporary life. In 2016, approximately 1.9 billion adults aged 18 and older were

classified as overweight. Among that total, almost 650 million adults were classified as obese. In that year, 39% of persons aged 18 and older were classified as overweight (Kassie et al. 2020; Quesada et al. 2020). The World Health Organization (WHO) has classified obesity as a

global epidemic. In Indonesia, 23% of adults were classified as obese in 2016, with a greater prevalence among women compared to males. According to the Indonesian Ministry of Health (2017), the global prevalence of overweight individuals now surpasses that of those who are malnourished (Lestari et al. 2021).

The 2013 Basic Health Research Results indicate that East Nusa Tenggara Province had the lowest adult obesity prevalence at 6.2%, while North Sulawesi had the highest at 24.0% (Lestari et al. 2021). Obesity and overweight are characterized by abnormal or excessive fat buildup in adipose tissue. White adipose tissue is formed by hyperplasia, volumetric expansion throughout development, and caloric surplus (Zhu et al. 2018). Researchers have extensively studied obesity in vitro using the 3T3-L1 cell line for adipogenesis and identified two key transcription factors: CCAAT-enhancer-binding proteins (C/EBP) and peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor γ (PPAR γ) (Ghosha et al. 2013; Zhang et al. 2016; Zhu et al. 2018). Normal adipose tissue modulates glucose metabolism via glucose transporter 4 (GLUT4), an essential mechanism (Ghosha et al. 2013; Kumar et al. 2016; Zhang et al. 2016). Lipid buildup in adipose tissue will further diminish insulin sensitivity, thereby affecting metabolic equilibrium (Altan et al. 2020; Li et al. 2021).

Inadequate management of obesity can significantly affect chronic diseases, including cardiovascular conditions, diabetes, and musculoskeletal disorders (Bhaskar et al. 2015; Salimzadeh et al. 2018). Obesity prevention is crucial to avert the onset of additional disorders and enhance quality of life. Consequently, we necessitate therapy to reduce the incidence of obesity. Non-pharmacological therapy, encompassing food and exercise, can avert obesity, while pharmacological therapy entails the administration of synthetic medications (Wong-a-nan et al. 2018; Lestari et al. 2020; Pucci et al. 2022). Simvastatin is a synthetic medication frequently employed to diminish elevated blood lipid levels. Nevertheless, high intake of simvastatin may result in detrimental health effects (Lestari and Rifa'i 2018; Lestari et al. 2020). Therapeutic interventions aimed at preventing obesity necessitate the use of natural components to effectively diminish or avert elevated body fat levels and obesity.

Currently, there is an increasing inclination among individuals to reestablish a connection with nature via traditional medicine that utilizes natural components. Garlic (*Allium sativum* L.) is a natural component with the potential to address obesity. Single garlic, a medicinal plant found in Indonesia, has a higher concentration of therapeutic compounds than compound garlic and offers numerous benefits in treating conditions such as obesity, hypertension, hypercholesterolemia, diabetes, antiviral, antifungal, anticancer, antibacterial, hepatoprotective, and rheumatoid arthritis (Lestari and Rifa'i 2018; Tesfaye 2021). It functions as a prophylactic for atherosclerosis, an inhibitor of neoplastic growth, a treatment for urinary tract ailments, and a therapy for respiratory conditions.

Some of the chemicals that are found in garlic are alliin, DATS, DADS, E/Z-ajoene, S-allyl-cysteine sulfoxide (alliin), S-allyl-cysteine (SAC), and diallyl sulfide (DAS) (Lestari et al. 2019; Ferioli et al. 2020). The process of reducing blood pressure Allicin reduces blood cholesterol by directly blocking the HMG-CoA reductase enzyme and thus obstructing the conversion of HMG-CoA to mevalonate. After that, the mevalonate changes into squalene, lanosterol, dihydrolanosterol, 8-dimethylsterol, 7-dihydrocholesterol, and finally cholesterol (Borlinghaus et al. 2014; De Greef et al. 2021). Use garlic to counteract the impact of high-fat and high-calorie diets on obesity. Even so, the disulfide bonds in allicin are very reactive and unstable, which makes it less stable and less soluble in water (Shang et al. 2019; Miasih et al. 2022). Allicin is vulnerable to heat, light, and oxidants, and it may irritate the human gastrointestinal mucosa upon direct contact. The gastrointestinal system recognizes a significantly low bioavailability of allicin (Gitin et al. 2014; Fitriana et al. 2019; Lestari et al. 2019). We need to develop a more acceptable delivery mechanism for a single garlic extract (SGE).

An effectively engineered drug delivery system can address numerous issues associated with traditional therapy and enhance the therapeutic efficiency of the delivered medication (Natrajan et al. 2015; Witika et al. 2020). A delivery agent must arrive in the target tissue in an optimal quantity and at the appropriate time, with reduced toxicity and minimal adverse effects, to attain maximum therapeutic efficacy. Researchers have already found that an SGE mixed with the Self Emulsifying Drug Delivery System (SNEDDS) can help reduce inflammation in 3T3-L1 cell lines (El Baroroh et al. 2024). In addition to lipid-based methods, encapsulation offers a viable solution to the challenges of poor water solubility and diminished bioavailability of substances throughout the digestive tract (Khorshidian et al. 2019; Ekawati et al. 2022). Recent investigations have focused on creating biodegradable natural polymers for the production of microparticles as drug delivery agents (Sorasithiyankarn et al. 2018). The pharmaceutical and food industries extensively utilize chitosan and alginate due to their non-toxic nature (Natrajan et al. 2015; Filho et al. 2019; Savic et al. 2022). The dependence of encapsulation on particle size, which influences chemical release, can significantly enhance its bioavailability (Adineh et al. 2020; Ekawati et al. 2022).

This study aims to develop an encapsulation of chitosan-alginate for the delivery of active components from a SGE (E-SGE) and to evaluate its efficacy as a weight loss supplement on 3T3-L1 cells in vitro. The restricted bioavailability of specific active components in single garlic upon digestion, which limits their effectiveness, underpins this progression. We expect that E-SGE technology will protect active compounds and enhance their effective delivery to targets. We anticipate this innovation will tackle hyperlipidemia, a primary contributor to obesity. E-SGE offers a promising method as an effective and innovative anti-obesity agent.

Materials and methods

Materials

The materials utilized in this study include single garlic sourced from Ngadas, Malang, East Java, Indonesia; ethanol (Merck, Germany); chitosan and alginate (both from Sigma-Aldrich, Germany); Tween-80 (Sigma-Aldrich, Germany); acetic acid, NaOH, and CaCl₂ (Merck, Germany); aquaproteinjection (PT. Ikapharmindo Putramas, Indonesia); sodium phosphate anhydrides (Na₂HPO₄), sodium dihydrogen phosphate (NaH₂PO₄), and sodium chloride (NaCl) (Nacalai Tesque Inc., Japan); deionized water (DI water) (Otsuka®, Indonesia); IBMX (MP Biomedicals, USA), insulin (Lavenis, India), dexamethasone (TCI, Japan); MTT reagent (Nacalai Tesque Inc., Japan); PPAR γ primary antibody (abcam, USA); C/EBP α , GLUT4, and adiponectin primary antibodies (Invitrogen, USA); dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) (Merck, Germany); paraformaldehyde (PFA) (TCI, Japan); bovine serum albumin (BSA) (BioWest, France); Triton X (Merck, Germany); goat anti-mouse rhodamine (Invitrogen, USA) and goat anti-rabbit fluorescein isothiocyanate (FITC) secondary antibodies (abcam, USA).

Methods

Single garlic extraction

A total of 1 kg of finely ground single garlic was macerated in 3 L of 70% ethanol for 3 × 24 hours. The mixture was filtered using filter paper to obtain the filtrate. The collected filtrate was then evaporated using a rotary evaporator IKA RV 10 digital V-C (IKA, Germany) to remove the solvent, leaving Single Garlic Extract (SGE). The obtained extract was stored in a refrigerator at 4 °C (Lestari et al. 2023).

Preparation of encapsulated SGE (E-SGE)

The encapsulation components consisted of an alginate solution dissolved in 0.5% Tween-80 (0.6 mg/mL), a chitosan solution in 1% acetic acid (0.6 mg/mL, pH 5), and a CaCl₂ solution in distilled water (0.67 mg/mL). E-SGE was prepared using the ionic gelation method, where each component was gradually added and mixed until homogeneous using a magnetic stirrer (Thermoline cimarec, USA), an ultra-turrax (IKA-WERKE, Japan), and sonication (IWAKI, Japan) to enhance stability and particle distribution. The resulting E-SGE product was stored at 4 °C to maintain its quality and stability (Natrajan et al. 2015; Lestari et al. 2023).

Morphological characterization of E-SGE using scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

E-SGE subjected to spray drying was used in this analysis. The spray drying process transformed the nanoencapsulation solution into a dry powder form. The E-SGE solution was sprayed through a nozzle and rapidly dried using hot air at a controlled temperature. The resulting dry powder

was collected in a storage container. A sample of 0.5 g of the E-SGE powder was analyzed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (FEI Quanta FEG 650, USA) at the Central Life Science Laboratory of Universitas Brawijaya (LSIH-UB) to observe surface morphology and particle distribution in detail (Natrajan et al. 2015).

The 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT) cytotoxicity assay of E-SGE on the 3T3-L1 cell line

Pre-adipocyte 3T3-L1 cells were obtained from the Laboratory of Structure, Development, and Physiology of Animals, Biology Department, Science and Mathematics Faculty, Universitas Brawijaya. The media consists of Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM), 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS), and 1% penicillin-streptomycin. The culture was maintained in a 25 cm² tissue flask under incubation conditions of 37 °C with 5% CO₂ until approximately 80% confluency was reached, at which point the cells were harvested.

A total of 5 × 10³ cells were seeded into 100 μ L of culture media in each well of a 96-well plate. After washing with 1 × PBS, 100 μ L of culture media containing E-SGE at various concentrations (62.5, 125, 250, 500, 1000, 2000, and 4000 μ g/mL, n = 3) was added to the wells, followed by 24 hours of incubation. At the end of the incubation period, the culture media was removed, and the cells were washed again with PBS.

Subsequently, 100 μ L of 3-[4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl]-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT) solution was added to each well, except for the blank, and the plate was incubated for 2–4 hours to allow purple formazan crystals to form. The reaction was stopped by adding 100 μ L of DMSO to dissolve the crystals, and the absorbance was measured using a microplate reader at a wavelength of 595 nm. Cell viability was calculated using Formula 1. (Miasih et al. 2022; El Baroroh et al. 2024).

$$\% \text{ Cell Viability} = \frac{A_{cc} - A_s}{A_{cc}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Noted:

Acc: Absorbance of the control cells

As: Absorbance of the sample

Modeling adipogenesis and lipid accumulation profiling with Oil Red O staining in 3T3-L1 cells

In the differentiation experiment, the cell line was first cultured until reaching 80% confluency. Two days post-confluency, differentiation of preadipocytes into mature adipocytes was initiated. The induction process involved adding a mixture containing 1 μ g/mL insulin, 0.25 μ M dexamethasone, and 0.5 mM 3-isobutyl-1-methylxanthine (IBMX) to complete DMEM. After 72 hours, the media was replaced with fresh complete DMEM supplemented with 1 μ g/mL insulin, with subsequent media changes every two days to ensure sufficient nutrient supply.

The E-SGE treatment began concurrently with differentiation induction on day 8 and continued through the differentiation period until day 12. E-SGE was administered at concentrations of 6.25 ppm, 125 ppm, and 250 ppm. Lipid accumulation in the cells was assessed using Oil Red O (ORO) staining.

On day 12, differentiation was halted, and staining was performed. The cells were washed twice with PBS, fixed in 10% formalin for 30–60 minutes, washed with 60% isopropyl alcohol and PBS, and then air-dried. The ORO solution was added and incubated for 30 minutes. Lipid droplets were subsequently rinsed three times with PBS and observed under a microscope (Lim et al. 2014).

Immunocytochemistry protein expression in the 3T3-L1 cell line

Protein expression associated with adipogenesis (C/EBP- α , PPAR- γ , GLUT-4, and adiponectin) was analyzed using immunocytochemistry (ICC) following treatment with E-SGE. Differentiated 3T3-L1 cells were treated from day 8 to day 12 with E-SGE, at concentrations of 6.25 ppm, 125 ppm, and 250 ppm. The cells were then fixed with 150 μ L of 4% paraformaldehyde for 5 minutes, washed twice with 300 μ L PBS, and incubated with 300 μ L of 0.5% Triton-X for 30 minutes to enhance membrane permeability.

After incubation with 3% BSA for 30 minutes, the cells were treated with primary antibodies against PPAR- γ , GLUT4, adiponectin, and C/EBP- α , followed by overnight incubation. After two washes with PBS, the cells were incubated for 1 hour with secondary antibodies: rhodamine (for PPAR- γ and adiponectin) and FITC (for GLUT4 and C/EBP- α). After the final wash, protein expression was observed using a fluorescence microscope in a dark room at the Integrated Laboratory Universitas Negeri Malang using an upright fluorescence microscope (Nikon Eclipse, Japan), and fluorescence intensity was calculated using ImageJ (Hou et al. 2014; Wong-a-nan et al. 2018).

Statistical analysis

SEM data analysis was presented descriptively. All quantitative data were expressed as mean \pm SD. The expression of C/EBP- α , PPAR- γ , GLUT-4, and adiponectin using ICC was statistically analyzed using one-way ANOVA, followed by the DMRT test at a significance level of $p < 0.05$.

Results and discussion

Sodium alginate and chitosan were natural active ingredients used in functional foods. In this study, sodium alginate and chitosan were used as encapsulating materials, which could effectively encapsulate SGE. The use of these two materials aimed to protect the active compounds in SGE, thereby improving its stability and bioavailability. The surface morphology of the nanoparticles was examined using SEM. The measured primary particles had a diameter of 865.4 nm (Fig. 1), indicating that the particles are in the micrometer size range and are highly suitable for drug delivery system (DDS) applications based on microencapsulation. Morphologically, the particles appeared nearly spherical with a smooth surface. These results are consistent with previous studies, which reported that chitosan-alginate encapsulation can produce spherical, well-defined, regular, and smooth shapes (Zohri et al. 2010; Tao et al. 2019; Villate et al. 2023). In addition, the surface of the microcapsules was also observed to be porous. It has been reported that the synthesized microencapsulates have a rough and porous surface (Fig. 1). Porosity can influence the retention, protection, and release of bioactive compounds, as well as stability and bioaccessibility (Villate et al. 2023).

The toxicity of E-SGE was evaluated using the MTT method on 3T3-L1 cells to assess the effect of different concentrations on cell viability. The findings indicated a

Figure 1. The SEM results of E-SGE at a 30,000 \times magnification showed spherical with a smooth surface.

dose-dependent reduction in cell viability corresponding to the increasing concentration of E-SGE. At the lowest concentration of 62.5 ppm, cell viability was significantly elevated, measuring $122.00 \pm 20.83\%$, suggesting possible cell proliferation or metabolic stimulation at low concentrations. This indicates that E-SGE may improve cellular activity at certain lower concentrations. Cell viability decreased to $100.44 \pm 16.80\%$ at a concentration of 250 ppm and $94.71 \pm 7.98\%$ at 500 ppm. This shows that E-SGE does not harm 3T3-L1 cells in this concentration range. The decrease in cell viability at these concentrations indicates that the proliferative effect of E-SGE starts to decline, yet it remains within acceptable limits for therapeutic use. The reduction in cell viability is likely attributable to the accumulation of bioactive compounds, including allicin and ajoene, which affect cell metabolism and dynamics (Lestari et al. 2022; Miasih et al. 2022; Lestari et al. 2023). The IC_{50} value of 920.44 ppm shows the concentration of E-SGE that has a significantly negative impact on cell viability (Fig. 2). This value sets the toxic level (Hadidi et al. 2018; Nordin et al. 2018).

Figure 2. Toxicity profile of encapsulated single garlic extract (E-SGE) in 3T3-L1 cells, showing the effect of different concentrations on cell viability.

At elevated quantities of 500 ppm and 1000 ppm, cell viability significantly diminished to $59.99 \pm 6.50\%$ and $45.23 \pm 15.87\%$, respectively. This reduction indicates that E-SGE began to exhibit cytotoxic effects on cells at these concentrations. The adverse effects may be attributed to the high concentration of bioactive compounds in garlic extract, such as allicin, which can disrupt cell membrane integrity or interfere with intracellular organelle function at elevated levels (Lestari et al. 2022; Lestari et al. 2023; Rahma et al. 2024). This impact is crucial to evaluate when establishing the safe concentration of E-SGE, particularly for medicinal supplement applications. At the maximum concentration of 2000 ppm, cell viability reached its nadir at $40.03 \pm 13.28\%$, signifying a substantial toxic impact (Fig. 2). This indicates that E-SGE, at this concentration, is inappropriate for therapeutic application due to its potential to induce considerable cellular damage. The findings of this toxicity assessment suggest that E-SGE is safe for usage at low to medium concentrations (≤ 250 ppm);

however, at elevated concentrations (>500 ppm), there exists a potential risk of toxicity that must be taken into account for clinical applications. Consequently, identifying the correct dosage is essential to harness the anti-obesity properties of E-SGE while avoiding severe side effects. Therefore, the chitosan-alginate encapsulation system becomes crucial in ensuring the safe application of E-SGE by mitigating the potential toxicity at higher concentrations, thus allowing for the controlled release of active compounds while preserving cell viability (Yu et al. 2018; Ding et al. 2019; Lestari et al. 2023).

The chitosan-alginate encapsulation system is very important for reducing the cell-damaging effects of Single Garlic Extract (SGE) at high concentrations. This process involves the formation of a barrier that safeguards cells and regulates the release of active compounds (Lestari et al. 2023). Chitosan is cationic, so it interacts electrostatically with negatively charged alginate (Rivera et al. 2015; Sorasitthyanukarn et al. 2019). This makes a stable matrix that holds the bioactive SGE components. This matrix keeps the cells from being exposed right away to high levels of compounds that could kill them, like allicin and ajoene, which are known for having important biological effects (Khorshidian et al. 2019; Lestari et al. 2023; Lestari et al. 2023). The encapsulation allows for the controlled and long-lasting release of active compounds (Lestari et al. 2023). This keeps the therapeutic effects at safe levels and prevents sudden increases that could damage or stress cells (Sorasitthyanukarn et al. 2019). The biocompatible properties of chitosan and alginate decrease adverse interactions with cell membranes, thereby lowering the risk of toxicity (Natrajan et al. 2015; Ahmad et al. 2022). This controlled delivery system enhances the anti-obesity effects of E-SGE by maintaining cell viability and functionality. This illustrates the significance of encapsulation in achieving a balance between safety and effectiveness in clinical environments. This controlled release system not only maximizes the therapeutic potential of E-SGE but also minimizes the risk of cytotoxicity, which is associated with the high concentrations of bioactive compounds like allicin, ajoene, and other sulfur-containing compounds (El Baroroh et al. 2020; Anggraini et al. 2022; Miasih et al. 2022). These molecules are known for their potent biological activities, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial properties, but they can also disrupt cellular homeostasis when present in excessive amounts (Ilmawati et al. 2017; Lestari et al. 2023; Lestari et al. 2023). Allicin, for instance, can induce oxidative stress and alter mitochondrial function, leading to cell apoptosis or necrosis (Lawson and Hunsaker 2018; Fitriana et al. 2019; Dhakar et al. 2023).

Lipid accumulation in 3T3-L1 cells was observed using an inverted microscope. Based on Fig. 3, the results visually showed lipid accumulation in the differentiation control treatment and the overall E-SGE treatment group. Microscopic visualization revealed a reduction in lipid accumulation in 3T3-L1 cells after treatment with E-SGE at concentrations of 62.5 ppm, 125 ppm, and 250 ppm compared with the differentiated control group (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. The lipid accumulation in the 3T3-L1 cell line after E-SGE treatment was visible, with varying degrees of lipid accumulation at different concentrations A. Untreated; B. Differentiated cells; C. E-SGE 62.5 ppm; D. E-SGE 125 ppm; and E. E-SGE 250 ppm; 100x magnification.

Furthermore, after treatment with E-SGE at various concentrations, a decrease in lipid expression in 3T3-L1 cells during differentiation induction was observed. It was suspected that *Allium* had benefits in the treatment of obesity through mechanisms such as the inhibition of adipogenesis, increased energy expenditure, and its effect on the expression of inflammatory mediators in serum. The synthesis of alliin (*S*-allyl-L-cysteine sulfoxide, SACSO), a major component in garlic, had been reported to play a role in reducing adipogenesis in 3T3-L1 adipocytes. Previous research was the first to reveal the direct effects of alliin, a bioactive compound in *Allium sativum*, on adipogenesis. This effect was demonstrated by the reduction

in the expression of Akt and PI3K, which are key players in the adipogenesis process (Li et al. 2021) (Savova et al. 2023). Ajoene, another bioactive compound from garlic, was also reported to effectively inhibit adipogenesis. Studies had shown that treatment with ajoene during the preadipocyte differentiation phase resulted in a significant reduction in lipid accumulation, as evidenced by decreased lipid droplet formation observed through Oil Red O staining (Ambati et al. 2008). Following these findings, the study further explored the effects of E-SGE on the expression of GLUT4, adiponectin, C/EBP α , and PPAR γ , all of which play important roles in the regulation of adipogenesis and glucose metabolism.

The expression of these four proteins serves as a crucial indicator in adipogenesis and glucose metabolism. The immunocytochemistry (ICC) staining results on 3T3-L1 cells indicated variability in green fluorescence levels for C/EBP α and GLUT4 protein expression across different treatments, and red fluorescence showed level of adiponectin and PPAR γ (Fig. 4). GLUT4 expression exhibited varying patterns. The differentiation control group had the highest intensity (36.82 ± 2.79 AU), which shows that mature adipocytes need to use glucose more efficiently. In contrast, cell control (untreated) exhibited basal levels of GLUT4 expression in preadipocytes, measured at 10.63 ± 0.66 AU. When 62.5 ppm E-SGE was added, the GLUT4 intensity was 22.16 ± 1.42 AU. This was less than the differentiation control but more than the cell control. GLUT4 expression decreased to 15.97 ± 9.39 AU at 125 ppm and 9.39 ± 0.62 AU at 250 ppm, with the highest concentration yielding the lowest value (Fig. 5). GLUT4 expression decreases at elevated concentrations, indicating that E-SGE may inhibit glucose uptake in adipocytes and potentially prevent fat accumulation (Bhattacharya et al. 2019).

Adiponectin is known as an insulin-sensitizing hormone produced and secreted by white adipocytes. On day 12, the cells were harvested. A significant increase in adiponectin levels was observed in the E-SGE-treated groups compared to the differentiation control (Fig. 5). The results showed that the best concentrations of MCA-SGE, 62.5 ppm (20.18 ± 2.14 AU) and 125 ppm (16.16 ± 1.34 AU), significantly increased ($p < 0.05$) adiponectin levels during differentiation compared to the differentiation control (9.84 ± 1.06 AU). On the other hand, the findings indicated that the expression level of C/EBP α in differentiation control (37.34 ± 4.95 AU) significantly exceeded that in untreated cells (15.42 ± 1.74 AU) (Fig. 5). It seems that adipocyte differentiation greatly raises the activity of this transcription factor, which controls genes related to the growth of mature adipocytes. Administration of E-SGE demonstrated a concentration-specific suppressive effect on C/EBP α expression. At a concentration of 62.5 ppm, C/EBP α expression decreased to 8.03 ± 1.01 AU. In contrast, at concentrations of 125 ppm and 250 ppm, expression increased to 15.92 ± 1.11 AU and 16.16 ± 1.53 AU, respectively, nearing the levels observed in control cells. Low concentrations suggest an inhibitory effect on adipogenesis, while elevated concentrations indicate a

Figure 4. Fluorescence intensity of GLUT4, adiponectin, C/EBP α , and PPAR γ protein expression in 3T3-L1 cells across different treatments with E-SGE; 400X magnification.

cell's tolerance to the active compounds present in SGE. Based on the data obtained, E-SGE significantly reduced PPAR- γ expression in 3T3-L1 cells ($p < 0.05$). The lowest expression was observed at a concentration of 62.5 ppm (3.06 ± 0.22 AU), which was significantly different from the differentiation control (30.63 ± 1.39 AU). Additionally, the other concentration groups (E-SGE 125 ppm and 250 ppm) also showed lower values compared to the differentiation control.

As the primary encapsulation materials, chitosan and alginate significantly influence how effectively the E-SGE formulation alters the expression of GLUT4, adiponectin, C/EBP α , and PPAR γ . Chitosan, a cationic polymer, exhibits distinct properties enabling electrostatic interactions with negatively charged molecules, including lipids (Sorasitthyanukarn et al. 2019; Lestari et al. 2023). By blocking the C/EBP α expression pathway, chitosan stops fat from building up in adipocytes and stops adipocytes from differentiating (Cho et al. 2008; Ding et al. 2019; Che et al. 2021). Specifically, the cationic properties of chitosan enhance the stability of encapsulation by effectively preventing digestive enzymes from breaking down SGE active compounds (Lestari et al. 2023). This protection enables active compounds, including allicin and ajoene, to achieve

greater efficacy in reaching biological targets (Khorshidian et al. 2019; Lestari et al. 2023). Conversely, alginate, being anionic, significantly aids in the establishment of a stable encapsulation matrix (Khorshidian et al. 2019; Lestari et al. 2023). This matrix preserves the capsule structure while facilitating the controlled release of active compounds in the intended environment (Natrajan et al. 2015; Liu et al. 2019). The only active compound in SGE can effectively change the expression of GLUT4 and C/EBP α because alginate helps with a slow and precise release mechanism. The negatively charged alginate and positively charged chitosan interact with each other in ionic ways that make encapsulation stronger. This creates a beneficial delivery system (Ghosha et al. 2013; Natrajan et al. 2015; Sorasitthyanukarn et al. 2019; Ahmad et al. 2022). The efficacy of chitosan and alginate in the controlled protection and release of individual active compounds in SGE establishes a robust foundation for understanding the mechanisms by which allicin and ajoene inhibit the expression of GLUT4, adiponectin, C/EBP α , and PPAR γ in 3T3-L1 cells (Ambati et al. 2009; Li et al. 2021).

Adiponectin promotes the proliferation and differentiation of preadipocytes into adipocytes through the sustained increase of transcription factors involved in the cell

Figure 5. E-SGE treatment of 3T3-L1 cells led to concentration-dependent changes in key markers, specifically GLUT4, adiponectin, C/EBP α , and PPAR γ expression, which contributed to glucose uptake, adipogenesis, lipid metabolism, and adipocyte differentiation (* $p < 0.05$).

differentiation process. A possible explanation is that the treatments delays cell proliferation development, resulting in lower adiponectin levels compared to the control group (Hengpratom et al. 2020). Adiponectin activates AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK), which in turn enhances the expression of PPAR γ . This promotes adipocyte differentiation and lipid metabolism, leading to the transcription of genes involved in fat storage and insulin sensitivity. Adiponectin binds to its receptors, AdipoR1 and AdipoR2, activating signaling pathways that increase PPAR- γ activity. This interaction is crucial for regulating adipogenesis and maintaining glucose homeostasis, enhancing fat storage and insulin sensitivity. Adiponectin also increases glucose uptake in adipocytes by activating PPAR- γ , which boosts GLUT-4 expression. This activation promotes the translocation of GLUT-4 to the plasma membrane, enhancing glucose uptake in response to insulin, and improving insulin sensitivity and metabolic regulation (Brody et al. 2009; Kopp et al. 2014).

Adiponectin enhances the expression of C/EBP- α , which works together with PPAR- γ to promote adipocyte differentiation. C/EBP- α is crucial for the early stages of adipogenesis and aids in the formation of mature adipocyte phenotypes. The interaction between adiponectin and C/EBP- α can create a positive feedback loop that strengthens the expression of adipogenic genes, supporting the differentiation process in 3T3-L1 cells (Kim et al. 2015). Research has shown that alliin can restore some levels of adiponectin in adipocytes stimulated by lipopolysaccharide (LPS). In experiments with 3T3-L1 adipocyte cell lines, treatment with alliin (at a concentration of 0.1 mM) resulted in a slight increase in adiponectin production (Quintero-Fabián et al. 2013).

The expression of the transcription factor C/EBP α represents one of these pathways (Valli et al. 2018). Decreasing C/EBP α expression inhibits the activation of genes

involved in adipocyte formation, thus preventing fat tissue accumulation (Martínez et al. 2020; Josan et al. 2021). Allicin is the source of the compound ajoene (Martins et al. 2016). This mechanism inhibits fat accumulation in adipocytes by reducing GLUT4 expression, a protein that facilitates glucose uptake in adipose cells (Bhattacharya et al. 2019). It works better when allicin and ajoene are combined in the encapsulated form of E-SGE than when SGE is used alone (Lestari et al. 2023; Lestari et al. 2023; Rahma et al. 2024). Encapsulation helps the controlled release of active compounds, which makes their biological effects last longer at certain concentrations. According to the results, the best amount of E-SGE stops adipogenesis by lowering the levels of C/EBP α and GLUT4 while keeping cells alive. Low concentrations (62.5 ppm) significantly decreased C/EBP α expression, whereas higher concentrations (125 ppm and 250 ppm) had a more pronounced effect on reducing GLUT4 levels. This suggests that E-SGE effectively stops adipocyte differentiation and changes how glucose is used in the body, making it a possible natural compound for treating obesity (Bhattacharya et al. 2019; Balogun and Kang 2021; Lestari et al. 2023).

PPAR- γ , the “master regulator” of adipogenesis, plays a crucial role in the development and function of adipose tissue. It coordinates genes involved in fat storage and metabolism, promoting lipid storage genes such as FABP4 and FASN, while suppressing lipolysis genes. This regulation helps maintain lipid storage and energy homeostasis in mature adipocytes. The mechanism of PPAR- γ activation begins when a ligand, which can be a hormone, free fatty acids, fatty acids, derivatives, or synthetic drugs, binds to the nuclear receptor. PPAR- γ then forms a heterodimer with the retinoid X receptor (RXR), which enhances the expression of adipogenic genes and proteins, including leptin and GLUT4 (Hengpratom et al. 2020).

Previous studies have shown that alliin, a bioactive compound from garlic, significantly reduces PPAR- γ expression on day 7 of adipogenic induction. Additionally, alliin affects the upstream signaling pathway by inhibiting the expression of PI3K and Akt, which are crucial for activating downstream targets like PPAR- γ . In contrast, alliin enhances the expression of the MAPK and ERK pathways on day 7, indicating a complex interaction between these signaling cascades during adipogenesis (Li et al. 2021). Di-allyl trisulphide (DATS) significantly increases adiponectin production in 3T3-L1 adipocytes and reduces the levels of adipogenesis-related genes, including PPAR- γ . DATS is capable of inhibiting adipogenesis in 3T3-L1 adipocytes, possibly through the regulation of genes involved in lipogenesis, lipolysis, and adipokines (Chang et al. 2015). In addition to the bioactive compounds found in single garlic, anti-adipogenesis effects can also be observed in the encapsulating material, chitosan. Chitosan has been shown to inhibit the differentiation of preadipocytes into adipocytes by regulating key transcription factors of adipogenesis, such as PPAR- γ and C/EBP α , by reducing their expression and lipid accumulation in adipocytes (Abd El-Hack et al. 2023). The anti-adipogenesis potential of chitosan has also been reported. Chitosan derivatives have shown anti-obesity activity by reducing lipid accumulation and suppressing the expression of SREBP1 and C/EBP- α in 3T3-L1 cells. Additionally, chitosan derivatives significantly increase the expression of preadipocyte factor 1 while inhibiting the promoters of genes related to adipocyte fatty acid-binding proteins, lipoprotein lipase, fatty acid synthase, and leptin (Shagdarova et al. 2023).

Conclusion

The encapsulation of Single Garlic Extract (SGE) using chitosan-alginate demonstrates promising potential as an anti-adipogenesis treatment. E-SGE shows high safety levels, maintaining cell viability across all tested concentrations. Its anti-adipogenic effects are evident in reducing fat accumulation in 3T3-L1 cells and downregulating key adipogenic markers such as PPAR- γ and C/EBP- α . Additionally, E-SGE enhances the expression of GLUT4 and adiponectin, further supporting its ability to mitigate fat formation. These findings highlight E-SGE as a safe and effective natural candidate for obesity management, warranting further investigation in *in vivo* models.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors, or donors' representatives participating in the study.

This study does not involve experiments on animals or human subjects.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalized human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Author contributions

S.R.L. was responsible for conceptualizing the study design and manuscript preparation. S.S. and H.S. contributed to the methodology and manuscript review. P.E.S.D., D.N.R., and N.P. conducted the experimental study and data analysis. D.S.M., Y.A., and A.R.E.B. were involved in the experimental study, data analysis, as well as drafting and editing the manuscript. All authors reviewed and approved the final version of the manuscript.

Author ORCIDs

Sri Rahayu Lestari <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-9857-7781>

Suharti <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9849-8083>

Hendra Susanto <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3935-4848>

Yuslinda Annisa <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5758-9923>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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